

How spraying of graphene nanoplatelets changes mechanical properties of carbon fibre reinforced polymer?

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Introduction

Nanofillers such as **graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs)** have been used to enhance out-of-plane properties of carbon fibre epoxy laminates (CFRP).

Nanofillers can be introduced to CFRP by mixing with matrix or coating on fibres directly (dip coating, electrophoretic deposition or chemical grafting). Although these techniques have demonstrated the enhancement of out-of-plane properties of CFRP laminates, the control of nanofillers location and amount remains challenging.

The **spraying technique** to introduce GNPs have drawn increasing attention because of a simple implementation. The present research work describes the fabrication and testing of multiscale CFRP. Nanofillers solution was deposited on the unidirectional carbon fibre fabric using a spraying technique to reinforce the interlaminar properties of CFRP.

Spraying process

Materials: unidirectional carbon fibre fabric, IN2 epoxy resin (Easy Composites, UK), GNPs (xGNP Graphene Nanoplatelet – Grade C750) in the form of powder (Sigma Aldrich, Dorset, UK).

Figure 1: Spraying GNPs solution to the carbon fibre fabric

Manufacturing CFRP

Figure 2: Manufacturing process of CFRP laminates a) degassing resin, b) impregnation of carbon fibre fabric with resin, c) vacuum bagging curing.

Mechanical Testing

Three-point bending and short beam tests were conducted using the universal tensile machine (Tinus Olsen) to measure flexural modulus, strength and interlaminar shear strength according to BS EN ISO 14125 and BS EN ISO 14130 testing standards.

Figure 3: Representation of a) three point bending, b) short beam tests.

Results

Flexural properties

Laminate ID	UD 0° (Control CFRP)	UD 0° (CFRP+GNPs)	UD 90° (Control CFRP)	UD 90° (CFRP+GNPs)
Height (mm)	2.55±0.1	2.74±0.11	2.51±0.03	2.71±0.05
F_{max} (N)	513.0±36	546.4±78	40.0±2	47.0±4
E_f (GPa)	96.6±4.5	97.38±2.5	6.05±0.2	5.6±0.6
σ_f (MPa)	665.2±8.2	632.2±24.6	49.04±2.2	49.67±4.2

Table 1. Comparison of 0° and 90° flexural properties of the unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced laminate (control CFRP and CFRP reinforced GNPs).

Interlaminar shear strength

Figure 4: Load-displacement curves of control and GNPs sprayed laminate - short beam test results.

Conclusions

- Spraying GNPs/epoxy/ethanol solution directly on carbon fibre surface was tested to make GNPs reinforced interphase.
- Ethanol and PVP surfactant were identified as the solvent combination for GNPs dispersion and were used for spraying process
- **The introduction of GNPs increased some flexural and interlaminar properties of CFRP samples.** The extent of enhancement is smaller than expected. Flexural modulus in 0° GNPs sprayed laminate, and flexural strength of 90° GNPs sprayed laminate increase a little (1.2%).
- The weak adhesion of the GNPs coating to carbon fibre process was observed at the time of samples preparation. This could be caused by inappropriate curing conditions of sprayed fabric and commercial sizing on the fibres.
- **Spraying process shows a huge potential to be scaled up to industrial level** and allows for better control of nanofillers during the spraying process.
- Automation of this technique will advantageously lead to controllable process conditions, which allow to design and optimize the coating properties.

References

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